

A new observation of rice defoliator in Nepal

S. B. Pradhan, Entomology Division, Khumaltar Agriculture Station (KAS), Kathmandu, Nepal

A new pest of rice *Amata nr fortunei* Del'orza of the family Amatidae was observed Aug-Sep 1985 in the field and in the greenhouse at KAS. Infestation was much more severe in the greenhouse.

Both sexes are small black moths with yellow markings (see figure). The adult male is 1 cm long with black, feathery antennae; the female is 1.1 to 1.2 cm long with straight antennae.

Larvae are black with white hairs. Maximum length of the full-grown larva is 1.5 cm. The larvae coil their bodies and hang in a silken thread when disturbed. They are solitary and in the early stages feed on chlorophyll of the

Larva (a) and adults (b) of *Amata nr fortunei*, family Amatidae, found in Nepal.

rice leaves in parallel lines, giving the impression of hispa or leptispa damage. In later instars, the larvae feed on all the leaf but the midrib. Overall damage is similar to that of armyworm.

Pupation takes place within a papery cocoon at the base of the rice plant or on any nearby object. The moth emerges

in 14-17 d. The female lays its egg in the morning in nonoverlapping chains. Eggs are oval and creamy white. They were observed on both surfaces of rice leaves as well as on other objects.

Specimens were identified by A. T. Barrion, Entomology Department, IRRI. □

Effect of silicate materials on rice crop pests

S. Subramanian and A. Gopaldaswamy, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, India

We assessed the effect of sodium metasilicate (48.5% SiO₂), furnace slag (20.2% SiO₂), and rice husk (14.5% SiO₂) at 1 t SiO₂/ha on incidence of rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall), rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason, and leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guen.

Experimental soil was sandy clay

loam with pH 7.0, EC 0.25 dS/m, 0.72% organic C, and 55.4 ppm available Si (N.NaOHC, pH 4.0).

Rice husk, furnace slag, and sodium metasilicate significantly reduced the thrips population (see table). Although silicate materials did not have much influence on GM incidence at tillering, a significant decrease was observed at panicle initiation. The addition of silicate materials also reduced LF incidence during panicle initiation.

Rice husk was superior to furnace slag and sodium metasilicate in reducing LF incidence. □

Effect of silicate materials on incidence of rice pests. Tamil Nadu, India, 1985.

Treatment	Tillering		Panicle initiation	
	Thrips (no./leaf)	Gall midge (%)	Gall midge (%)	Leaf folder (%)
Control	10	11.3	24.7	28.0
Sodium metasilicate	6	9.8	23.1	21.8
Furnace slag	6	10.7	18.2	18.7
Rice husk	7	10.0	20.4	18.0
LSD (0.05)	1	ns	2.2	2.3

A rearing technique for *Conocephalus longipennis* (de Haan) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)

E. G. Rubia and B. M. Shepard, Entomology Department, IRRI

The grasshopper *C. longipennis* common in ricefields is considered a predator, but it has been shown to attack rice, especially developing grains. It has also been observed to feed on rice foliage and flowers.

As a predator, it attacks the eggs of

rice bugs, stem borers, and leaf folders and the nymphs and adults of hoppers, leaf folders, and whorl maggots.

To study its status as a predator or as a pest, a rearing method was needed.

Field-collected adult *C. longipennis* were confined on 45-d-old TN1 rice plants (see figure). Leaf sheaths bearing eggs were cut from rice plants and transferred to petri dishes lined with moist filter paper. Newly emerged first instars were transferred individually (to prevent cannibalism) to 15.0-cm test tubes (1.6 cm in diameter) and provided with southwestern corn borer diet.

Survival of *C. longipennis* using the mass rearing technique. IIRI insectary, 1986.

Stage	Insects reared (no.)	Surviving individuals (no.)	survival (%)
Egg to 1st instar	326	307	96
1st instar to adult	40	34	85

Third instars were transferred to 20.0-cm test tubes (2.5 cm in diameter) to complete nymphal development. Newly emerged adult males and females were confined in 30- × 22- × 52.5-cm rectangular mylar cages with separate petri dishes containing 2 g of corn borer diet and moist cotton on the bottom. The moist cotton provided water and served as a suitable substrate for oviposition.

C. longipennis completed its life cycle from egg to adult in 142 to 182 d, with 80% survival (see table). The corn borer diet was suitable for rearing the insect. □

Rearing field-collected grasshoppers in the laboratory.

Effect of insecticides on rice leaffolder (LF) eggs

N. Raju, M. Gopalan, and G. Balasubramanian, Centre for Plant Protection Studies, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied nine insecticides to determine their ovicidal efficacy on eggs of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) in the insectary. The experiment was in a completely randomized design with three replications, with each replication consisting of 20 eggs.

Male and female LF moths obtained from mass culture were introduced in tumbler pots containing 25-d-old rice seedlings. The tumbler pots were covered with glass chimneys 22 cm high and 7.5 cm in diameter. Oviposition was observed daily. Seedlings containing eggs were separated and planted in tumbler pots.

Insecticidal treatments were given with a hand atomizer; control pots received water spray. Hatching of larvae was recorded for each treatment.

Phosphamidon, quinalphos, and monocrotophos treatments had 100% egg mortality; fenthion followed with 96% mortality (see table). Endosulfan exhibited the least ovicidal action. □

Ovicidal action of insecticides on rice LF eggs. Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Concn. (%)	Mortality ^a (%)
Monocrotophos 36 WSC	0.05	100 a
Quinalphos 25 EC	0.05	100 a
Phosphamidon 85 WSC	0.045	100 a
Fenthion 100 EC	0.01	96 a
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	0.04	54 b
Malathion 50 EC	0.1	46 b
Dichlorvos 100 EC	0.02	42 b
Carbaryl 50 WP	0.1	42 b
Endosulfan 35 EC	0.07	21 c
No insecticide (control)	Water spray	11 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

Leaffolder (LF) resurgence and species composition in Pattambi, Kerala

L. Nadarajan and B. P. Skaria, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Pattambi, Kerala 679306, India

In field trials 1983-85 at Pattambi, LF damage was higher in maximum protection treatments (MPT) (see figure). In both the first crop (May-Aug) and second crop (Sep-Feb), MPT plots receiving carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) recorded higher LF damage (90% in the first crop, 55% in the second) than the no-insecticide plot.

Triazophos effectively controlled LF. Carbosulfan was no different from no insecticide. With synthetic pyrethroid, damage was 10-25%.

To corroborate these findings, we conducted an observational trial in 90-m² plots using EC (emulsifiable